

Study and Analysis of Computer Information Systems and Management Information Systems in Traditional Industrial Sectors

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Abstract

Modern 8th-century technology is crucial in information systems, enhancing business services and post-industrial efficiency in developing countries. Computer Information Systems (CIS) and Management Information Systems (MIS) support operations, planning, and decision-making functions. Digital technologies, such as IoT, have expanded operations handling, but resistance exists among staff and end users. Management processes are guided by goals and objectives, and control activities involve comparing actual performance to planned performance. The leather industry in India has experienced significant growth, but social change is influenced by technological, economic, political, or religious development. Computer Information Systems (CIS) have significantly impacted traditional industrial sectors in India, enhancing productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness in a global market. Key areas include enhanced operational efficiency, data management, and supply chain management, quality control, cost reduction, market adaptability, employment and skill development, sustainability and environmental impact, and compliance and reporting. CIS has enabled automation in manufacturing processes, real-time tracking of supply chains, and predictive maintenance in leading automotive plants. Digital tools for inventory and production planning have modernized operations in the textile industry, ensuring better resource management and reduced waste. CIS solutions have also been applied in agriculture, monitoring crop health, managing irrigation, and streamlining the food supply chain. The integration of CIS in these sectors has driven significant advancements, promoting sustainability and resource efficiency, and creating a need for new skill sets in the Indian workforce.

Keywords: Computer Communication System, Industry, Management Information System, Networks, Data Efficiency.

I Introduction

Modern 8th-century technology is a critical component in the context of information systems, as it plays a critical role in enhancing the quality of business services. In developing countries, computer and communication systems are essential for post-industrial efficiency[1]. These technologies can be beneficial for reducing waste and improving efficiency, but they also have potential dangers. High technology has dual benefits, as it allows for the analysis of complex tasks into simple tasks, which can be executed more efficiently[2]. Additionally, it is possible for employees to use robots to perform more complex tasks. In the case of a small business, the manager can maximize profits by utilizing the available resources. The majority of efficient information systems are not merely a luxury but a necessity for the business[3]. As the size of the firm increases, the situation demands that computer systems are used

effectively[4].

Fig.-1 Outline of the key areas where CIS has made significant contributions

The Computer Information System (CIS) is a relatively new tool for use in an organization, with the first computer being invented in 19 for business application, such as payroll processing[5]. Today, the frontiers in information processing are systems that provide information resources in support of managerial and decision-making functions[6]. A management information system (MIS) is an organization method of providing past, present, and projection information, relating to transactions and external intelligence. It supports the planning, control, and operational functioning of an organization by furnishing univocal information in the property till-fra to assist the decision-making process[7].

Fig.-2 Basic Networking Concept

A system can be defined as a combination of integrated elements with the purpose of achieving a specific objective. All systems have certain properties, such as environment interaction between their parts and with the target, and the necessity of all two million goals to "fulfil". In business, sub-systems, such as Doting. Finance and manufacturing, are the basic functional units. The Computer Information System and Network (CISM) project is broadly conceived international research study conducted by researchers in Austria, Germany, England, West Germany, and the United States[8]. The results show that computer information systems can be used in various countries, but they cannot be compared with the personnel functions of developed countries or with the undeveloped countries[9].

II. Literature Survey and Analysis

In recent years, digital technologies have significantly expanded the range of digital applications in operations handling[3]. Rapid cost reduction and increased sector flexibility have placed many organizations within the budget range of developing countries. The Internet of Things (IoT) has been the development of telecommunication systems, enabling users to access information simultaneously[10]. However, there is inherent resistance to new technology among operating staff and end users. It is important for any project not involving an organization to incorporate new technology into operations or services and take this resistance into account throughout the project[11]. A Management Information System (MIS) is an information system that provides necessary transaction processing for an organization, providing information and processing support for management and decision-making functions[12]. The computer-based information system is an essential field for the effective utilization of available resources[13]. A MIS is an integrated network system for a company to support operations, planning, and decision-making functions in an organization. Planning is a

future-oriented function, and managers should consider the role of information technology in their operations[14].

Fig.-3 Management Information System

The management process is guided by goals and objectives that originate from owners, government, society, or the organization itself. Managers translate these objectives into specific courses of action, such as structuring resources, staffing, and controlling activities[15]. In the manufacturing function, managers discharge their responsibilities by acquiring resources, coordinating resources, and coordinating activities. Controlling activities involve comparing actual performance to planned performance and initiating corrective action to remedy variances. This includes receiving reports of sub-standard sales, re-examine sales prices, and identifying additional resources. Managers also motivate, supervise, and compare actual sales to sales figures. The impact of computer information systems on the structure of the organization is significant[16]. The first study of the impact of computer systems on management predicted reduction in the average organization due to the rise of new computer technology. However, by the early 19th century, decisions were beginning to shift on different levels, with managers being able to control the organization more effectively[17]. In conclusion, the management process is guided by goals and objectives, involving various functions such as staffing, purchasing, and resource allocation[18]. By implementing these strategies, organizations can thrive in a constantly changing environment and adapt to changing circumstances.

III. Impacts of CIS in different sectors:

The leather industry is one of the oldest in India and other parts of the world, with a significant position in the global economy. It is characterised by an infinite variety of raw materials, including hides and skins from bovine, buffalo, pigs, and exotic animals. The Indian leather industry has seen significant growth in the last two decades, with significant participation in international fairs and advertisements for their products[17]. The leather industry is fashion-oriented, with quick changes in product design, colour, and quality. The manufacturing process of leather has evolved over time, with various processes and techniques developed. The raw materials used in leather production include hides and skins, which are obtained from livestock such as cattle, buffaloes, pigs, and pigs. The hide can be treated with sulphur extract or by heating it to inhibit the action of bacteria. After curing, the leather enters the tannery and is processed to create leather goods[19]. The final leather production process

involves several steps, including soaking the hides and skins to remove the soluble fats, external protective covering of fiber, fat, and soluble proteins required in the finished leather. This process is achieved through various methods, such as removing the fats, fleshing, and slicing. The skins are then shaped and shaped to achieve a soft and flaccid condition. The tanning process involves heating or steaming the hides with an infusion of pigeon or dog dung for several hours. This process is similar to the process for lighter skins, such as glove and fleeced goats and Ioroccos. The skins are then treated with a mixture of oil and acid to condition the leather for tanning. Pickled skins taken for vegetable tanning must be de-pickled if they have excess clay from pickling. The acid will result in poor strength and the leather will be susceptible to putrefaction. The process of tanning is crucial for the final finished product, as the soluble fats and proteins are removed from the hides and skins to ensure their proper condition.

IV. Impacts on Social Climate:

Social change in the leather goods industry in India is often a result of technological, economic, political, or religious development, but it can also be influenced by non-detrimental factors like natural latencies. The industry is largely practiced by the untouchable caste, who are considered the traditional 'prerogative' caste. The tanning and finishing industry in Tamil Nadu provided employment to 15,000 workers in the first factory in 1978-79, and the industry exported Rs.2,75.0 million worth of leather and leather products in 1918-79. However, the actual benefits have not reached the individual workers[18]. The tanning industry in Tamil Nadu was highly labour-intensive and produced predominantly silk for export. The intensification of the tanning industry led to the substitution of capital for labour and the installation of machines in the next factory. Housing for workers is a neglected aspect by employers, and this can lead to discontent among workers. If workers are not satisfied with their basic living conditions, it will result in resentments, unrest, and strikes. In the future, social incentives will be needed to keep workers happy and loyal to employers. The leather industry is experiencing a shift in the workforce, with many workers becoming more economically independent and self-aware[20]. This has led to increased social and economic status for workers, who are more receptive to external opportunities for education and career advancement. The future of the leather industry is expected to see more women continue working even after marriage and child-birth, improving the quality of life for workers. However, the traditional leather industry faces challenges such as lack of finance, technical knowledge, and the inability to procure quality raw materials. Government schemes to provide loans to traditional artisans have not been successful due to factors such as long and expensive procedures, lack of interest, and the risk of losing interest due to illness or injury. The government's efforts to address these issues are not always successful, as workers often face difficulties in obtaining loans and maintaining their livelihoods.

Fig.-4 Algorithm of Machine learning

V. Real Time Analysis and Reporting's:

Tate & Sons Limited (TBL) was established in 1962 as a large manufacturing company in the private sector of India, focusing on an extensive range of products in Bombay, Calcutta, Delhi, and Delhi, with regional offices in Madras, Rajasthan, Shadohi, and Agra. TBL has a large SCALE nufacturing of D. Ift Madya Pradesh for leather finishing, g_x.ent.l, ahee up~r., infr.rucural facilities for research and development, pilet plant for leather auxiliary auxiliaryries, and a number of ancillary and downst units[21]. TBL operates over 190 acres and is part of the T.u Group of Companies, which acts as one of the principal contributors of the Indian industry. TBL has a modern leather processing unit at Dewas"" backwasd ana in the Madya Pradesh, which is primarily export-based.

The unit has a leath.~ dlvl, len and olt'llents division, which focuses on the leather dyeing process, raw hide and skins, finished leather, and exports. The company has a central etch burd factory, a fully automated punch control system, and a central water bath. The text describes the process of tanning leather skins, focusing on the use of a hydraulic sprayed machine. The machine uses a hydraulic system to spray the leather surface, allowing for a more efficient and accurate process. The process involves a series of photo-electric cells that scan the leather surface, which are then counted and displayed on an illuminated display screen. The machine is designed to meet the demands of tanners who want soft, full-grain leather skins. The process of tanning leather skins involves several steps, including the use of a pressurized water bath, the use of a vacuum drying machine, and the use of a rotary press. The liquid is pumped from a bulk container, and the flow rate is controlled by a gear pump. The process of

tanning leather skins involves several steps, including the use of a pressurized water bath, the use of a vacuum drying machine, and the use of a rotary press. The process is controlled by a series of electronic and mechanical components, ensuring the highest quality and efficiency in tanning leather skins.

Conclusion and Future Scopes:

Computers have significantly changed the efficiency and effectiveness of organizations. The computer information management system ensures managers are equipped with the necessary information to make effective and prompt decisions as the situation demands. There is a continuous flow with day-to-day events and future forecasting, which may lead to unexpected interruptions and require effective control to ensure the organization's success. Managers should be capable of tackling unexpected incidents with managerial skills and strategies. There are different levels of management in an organization, with defined objectives or hand responsibilities. Managers can easily forecast and forecast profits with the help of computers. However, the technology may be misinterpreted as a misapplication of the ITRIX concept, and other cases may demand the capability of computer systems within lateral departments. In the British Glass Company, the budget preparation was coordinated through cooperation efforts in various functional areas. The computer information system allowed for more flexible reporting relationships, encouraging local control and not requiring full authentication of instructions through the finance head. In terms of employment, the introduction of computer technology has resulted in a change in the nature of jobs and skills required. The basic objective in computerization is to improve productivity and profitability of the organization. The leather industry is experiencing rapid changes due to the use of digital technology and changing attitudes. Traditional leather workers are often unaware of government schemes and face difficulties in accessing loans. Government and institutions should recognize and help the weakest sections of society, and provide support to those who are depressed and suppressed in society. Training programs should be implemented to educate these individuals and help them transition from their traditional professions to other jobs. The government should also use these people to frame the policies of the industry and provide equal justice to all. The structure of the leather industry is rapidly changing with the use of digital technology and changing attitudes. The information service department provides information to all levels of management, leading to decentralization. However, top-level management closely monitors the performance of lower-level management from a central point. The philosophy of management plays a significant role in the success of the leather industry.

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